

Physicochemical properties of parboiled and unparboiled discolored grains. Ibadan, Nigeria.

Property	Healthy raw	Discolored raw	Healthy parboiled	Discolored parboiled	CV	LSD (5%)
Dry weight (mg)/grain						
Rough rice	28.8	26.8	28.4	25.9	0.21	0.18
Brown rice	24.6	21.9	24.4	22.6	0.15	0.11
Milling yield (% of rough rice)						
Milled rice	73.6	71.3	79.0	77.0	1.03	2.45
Head rice	36.8	31.5	77.4	76.0	2.49	8.40
Milled rice						
Hardness (kg)	6	6	14	14	5.5	6.1
Chalkiness ^a	5	5	0	0	—	—
Discoloration (%)	3	5	9	20	—	—
Gelatinization temperature ^a	HI/I	HI/I	1	1	—	—
Cooking time (min)	25	24	24	24	1.46	ns
Amylose content (%)	14.9	13.4	14.2	13.8	1.19	0.54

^aStandard evaluation system for rice.

Complete slide sets of photos printed in Field problems of tropical rice, revised 1983, are available for purchase at \$50 (less developed country price) or \$60 (developed country price), including airmail postage and handling, from the Communication and Publications Department, Division R, IRRI, P. O. Box 933, Manila, Philippines. No orders for surface mail handling will be accepted.

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization DISEASE RESISTANCE

Field screening against tungro (RTV) in Lanrang, Indonesia

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Breeding lines from the Bogor Research

Lines identified as resistant to RTV and their reaction at 4, 6, 8 WT at Lanrang, South Sulawesi, Indonesia.

Line	RTV score ^a		
	4 WT	6 WT	8 WT
B6240-Mr-1-3-3	0	0	0
B6228-Mr-10-1-1-2	0	0	0
B6242-Mr-23-3-1	0	0	0
B6236-Mr-14-1-2	0	0	0
B6932-Mr-26-blk	0	0	0
B6025-Mr-56-1-3-2-0	0	0	0
B6209e	0	1	0
B6716-Mr-4-3	0	1	0
B6240-Mr-1-3-2	0	0	1
B6680-Mr-9-6	0	0	1
B6346-Mr-3-2-1	0	1	1
B6228-Mr-10-1-1-3	0	0	1
B6448-2-Mr-4-3-2	0	0	1
B6448-2-Mr-4-3-1	0	0	1
B6350-Mr-6-2-1	0	1	1
B6723-Mr-1-4	0	0	1
B6229-Mr-28-1-1-1	0	1	1
B6208e	1	3	3
B6234-Mr-14-2-3-1	0	1	3
B6007-Mr-34-1-1-2-0	0	1	3
B6058-Mr-16-2-3-3	0	1	3
B6733-Mr-2-2	0	1	3
B6058-Mr-14-2-3-2	0	1	3
B6228-Mr-47-4-3	0	1	3

Table continued

Line	RTV score ^a		
	4WT	6WT	8WT
B6443-10-Mr-1-1-2	0	1	3
B6228-Mr-47-4-1	0	1	3
B7000-Mr-8	0	1	3
B5960-Mr-18-9-3-0	1	3	3
B7004-Mr-1	1	3	3
B6553-Mr-1-1	0	1	3
B6058-Mr-19-2-1-2	0	1	3
B6682-Mr-1-2	0	1	3
B6471-Mr-6-3-1	0	1	3
B6548-Mr-1-2	0	1	3
B6058-Mr-19-2-1-1	0	1	3
M6964-Mr-4-3-3	0	1	3
B6448-2-Mr-4-3-1	0	1	3
B6058-Mr-19-2-3-2	0	1	3
B6446-25-Mr-2-14	0	1	3
B6207e	0	1	3

Institute for Food Crops (BORIF) were evaluated in the field during the 1986 monsoon season to identify sources resistant to RTV.

Each line was transplanted in 2 rows of 20 hills/row at 20- × 20-cm spacing. RTV-infected TN1 plants were transplanted in 1 row between each line.

The trial plot was fertilized at 90 kg N and 26 kg P/ha. RTV was scored by the Standard evaluation system for rice (SES) at 4, 6, and 8 wk after transplanting (WT).

Of 1,500 accessions screened, 56 were resistant to RTV (see table). □

Line	RTV score		
	4WT	6WT	8WT
B6678d	1	3	3
B5994-Mr-28-3-3-3-0	0	1	3
B6229-Mr-14-3-2-2	1	3	3
B5964-Mr-12-1-2-1	0	1	3
B6932-Mr-1-blk	0	1	3
B6229-Mr-28-1-1-2	0	1	3
B5960-Mr-18-8-1-1-0	1	3	3
B6932-Mr-10-blk	0	1	3
B6733-Mr-7-2	0	1	3
B5517f-Kn-22-0-0	1	3	3
B6932-Mr-11-blk	0	1	3
B6696-Mr-14-3	0	1	3
B6932-Mr-25-blk	0	1	3
B6680-Mr-9-3	0	1	3
B6058-Mr-19-2-1-2	0	1	3
B6679-Mr-23-2	0	1	3

^aBy the SES 0-9 scale.

Multilocational screening for bacterial blight (BB) resistance

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With increased irrigation facilities, rice has become a major food crop in Gujarat. It is grown predominantly in the south. BB (*Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae*), false smut (*Ustilaginoidea virens* now *Claviceps oryzae*), and blast